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ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ДЕЛОВОГО АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА: ВОЗНИКАЮЩИЕ ТРУДНОСТИ И РЕШЕНИЯ ДЛЯ ТЕСТИРОВАНИЯ

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Аннотация. Это исследование изучает эффективность платформ искусственного интеллекта в обучении английскому языку по сравнению с обучением исключительно по учебникам. Были изучены две группы студентов: одна группа использовала онлайн-платформу с поддержкой ИИ, а именно TurboLearn, другая полагалась только на учебники. После определённого периода обучения обе группы прошли тестирование через онлайн-платформу Examica для оценки своих знаний по деловому английскому языку. Результаты демонстрируют значительное преимущество группы, использовавшей платформы с ИИ, показывая более высокие результаты тестирования. Эти данные позволяют предположить, что платформы обучения на основе ИИ могут существенно повысить эффективность освоения языка. Исследование вносит вклад в то, что интеграция технологий ИИ может улучшить преподавание и обучение языкам.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, онлайн платформы, тестирование, обучение по учебникам, освоение языка

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHING BUSINESS ENGLISH: ENCOUNTERED CHALLENGES AND TESTING SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. This research investigates the efficiency of artificial intelligence platforms in teaching English when compared to solely book-based learning. Two groups of students were studied: one group utilized AI-assisted online platform, namely TurboLearn, another relied on textbooks only. After the specified instructional period, these two groups underwent standardized testing through the online platform examica to assess their Business English knowledge. The results demonstrate a significant advantage that the group using AI platforms have, demonstrating higher test scores. These findings lead to the assumption that AI-based learning platforms can significantly enhance language acquisition. The study contributes to the growing evidence that the integration of AI technologies can improve language teaching and learning.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, online platforms, testing, textbook-based learning, language acquisition

Introduction

AI is quickly changing education by making learning more personal, making instructors' jobs easier, and giving them useful help. Adaptive learning technologies, intelligent tutoring systems (ITS), and natural language processing (NLP) platforms are examples of educational technologies that are being used by students today. These technologies are specifically designed for students [7]. Arya and Verma and Silva et al. state that these systems provide rapid feedback, personalize information to each student, and continually monitor how well pupils are performing [1], [6]. Making lesson planning, maintaining attendance records, and grading are just a few of the tasks that teachers may receive assistance with through the use of artificial intelligence. This allows educators to have more time to become familiar with their students and make learning enjoyable [4]. According to Fitria, technology does not have the ability to provide the moral and empathic support that educators do [2]. Ifenthaler and Yau found that predictive analytics can assist schools in identifying pupils who are in risk early on [3]. One school district, for instance, made use of an AI-powered dashboard to discover which students were absent from school frequently and performing poorly on examinations. When anything goes awry, artificial intelligence's value becomes most apparent. Thanks to the implementation of solutions based on artificial intelligence, students were able to continue their education in regions that were impacted by conflict as well as during the COVID-19 pandemic. Adaptive learning technology enables students to carry on with their studies even when they do not have a full understanding of the content. Popenici and Kerr assert that educators play an essential role in cultivating critical thinking, ethical reasoning, and emotional growth—abilities that cannot be emulated by machines [5].

Methods

The mean percent scores of Group A (TurboLearn) and Group B (textbook-based) were compared. Descriptive statistics were calculated, and mean values were highlighted with approximate 95% confidence intervals to indicate the precision of the estimates. The confidence intervals provide a range in which the student population mean is expected to fall with 95% certainty. To test whether the difference in mean scores between the two groups was statistically significant, statistical tools were applied and analysis was conducted.

Results

There are a number of AI-powered systems that show how exciting and difficult AI may be in education, but for the sole purpose of our research, only one AI-assisted platform has been utilized to help students when getting ready for the formative test.

One of the best website to consider for study tools like flashcards, study notes and quizzes is TurboLearn that generates all the necessary materials by bringing together videos, lectures, and PDFs. It is especially useful for studying for tests because it can function on more than one device at the same time. Two separate groups of first-year students studied for the same formative assessment test. Group A utilized TurboLearn to make flashcards, study notes, and summaries from PDFs of lessons from the course-book. Group B used their own study habits and handwritten notes.

[AI-Powered Assistant | TurboLearn](#) – beneath you will find the study notes generated by TurboLearn AI based on the pdf document of the lesson on Economic Inequality provided.

Study Notes

Content Summary

This document defines economic inequality as disparities in wealth, assets, or income among individuals or populations. It categorizes countries into two main types based on per capita income: developed nations with high income and industrialization, and developing nations with lower income and less industrialization. Developing nations are further subdivided into moderately developed and less developed countries, each with distinct income ranges and geographical distributions.

Key Points

- Economic Inequality:** Refers to differences in wealth, assets, or income between individuals or populations.
- Country Categorization:** The world's countries are primarily divided into two types based on per capita income.
- Developed Nations:** Characterized by high industrialization, per capita income of \$12,000 or more, stable population growth, and high resource consumption.
- Developing Nations:** Less industrialized with lower per capita income, further divided into moderately developed and less developed categories.
- Moderately Developed Countries:** Per capita income between \$1,000 and \$12,000, with an average around \$4,000.
- Less Developed Countries:** Per capita income below \$1,000.

Developing Nations: A Spectrum of Economic Progress

- Broad Definition:** This category encompasses countries that are less industrialized and have lower per capita income levels.
- Sub-categories:** Developing nations are further divided into two distinct groups: moderately developed and less developed countries.

Moderately Developed Countries: The Middle Ground

- Income Range:** These countries have a per capita income falling between \$1,000 and \$12,000.
- Average Income:** The average per capita income for this group is approximately \$4,000.
- Geographic Distribution & Examples:** Recognizable moderately developed countries include Mexico, China, Indonesia, Jordan, Thailand, Fiji, and Ecuador. This category also includes numerous countries across Central and South America, northern and southern Africa, Southeast Asia, Eastern Europe, the former USSR, and many Arab states.

Less Developed Countries: The Lowest Income Bracket

- Income Threshold:** These nations have the lowest income levels, with a general per capita income of less than \$1,000.
- Geographic Concentration:** Less developed countries are predominantly found in eastern, western, and central Africa, India, and other parts of southern Asia.

Detailed Explanation

Economic Inequality: The Foundation of Disparity

- Economic inequality is observable in everyday life through differences in housing, transportation, and various activities.
- It fundamentally represents the gap in wealth, assets, or income that exists between individuals or entire populations.

Global Country Classification: A Two-Tiered System

- Countries are broadly classified into two main categories.
- This classification is primarily driven by **per capita income**, which signifies the average income earned by each person in a country.

Developed Nations: Pillars of Prosperity

- Characteristics:** These nations are highly industrialized and generally boast high per capita income levels.
- Income Threshold:** A country is typically considered developed if its per capita income is approximately \$12,000 or higher.
- Examples:** Prominent examples include the United States, Canada, Japan, South Korea, Australia, New Zealand, Scandinavian countries, Singapore, Taiwan, Israel, Western European nations, and certain Arab states.
- Resource Consumption:** Developed nations are also distinguished by their high consumption of natural resources per person, alongside stable population growth rates.

Key Concepts

- Economic Inequality:** The uneven distribution of income, wealth, and assets within a society or across different populations.
- Per Capita Income:** The average income earned per person in a country, calculated by dividing the total national income by the total population. It's a key metric for assessing a country's economic development level.
- Industrialization:** The process by which an economy is transformed from primarily agricultural to one based on the manufacturing of goods. Higher levels of industrialization are generally associated with higher economic development.
- Developed Nations:** Countries with advanced industrialization, high per capita income, high standards of living, and well-developed infrastructure.
- Developing Nations:** Countries that are in the process of industrialization and economic growth, typically characterized by lower per capita income and less developed infrastructure compared to developed nations.
- Moderately Developed Countries:** A sub-category of developing nations with intermediate levels of industrialization and income.
- Less Developed Countries:** A sub-category of developing nations with the lowest levels of industrialization and income.

Group A had the opportunity to practice their knowledge through the employment of this online AI-assisted platform to get ready for the test that was organized through the online tool www.examica.ai.

Test results of these two groups based on the score of minimum 0 and maximum 100 points expressed in per cents.

Group	N of students	Mean	SD	Median	Min	Max
Group A (TurboLearn)	25	86.6	5.90	85.0	75.0	95.0
Group B (Books)	28	66.7	12.0	70.0	30.0	85.0

Table 1: Test results of Groups A and B

The results of the comparative analysis carried out indicate a statistically significant difference in the test performance between Group A (students who prepared with the utilization of TurboLearn platform) and Group B (students who prepared solely with traditional paper-based materials, in our case, their books only). It can be highlighted that Group A achieved a significantly higher mean score ($M = 86.6$, $SD = 5.9$) compared to Group B ($M = 66.8$, $SD = 12.0$). Furthermore, the Effect size analyses (Cohen's $d = 2.05$; $r = 0.78$) indicate an extremely big difference, underlining that the TurboLearn group (Group A) outperformed the other group (Group B) both statistically and practically. On average, Group A scored approximately 20 percentage points higher than Group B. This difference is not only statistically significant but also very large in practical terms, which indicates that the choice of study and revision method made a real difference. The AI-assisted learning tool, in our case, TurboLearn AI appears to give students a strong advantage in preparing for Business English tests.

Bar Chart 1: Mean test scores of the Groups A and B

Histograms 1 and 2 indicating the test percent scores of Groups A and B

The obtained results indicate that Group A practicing through TurboLearn platform achieved a higher mean score ($M = 86,6\%$) compared to Group B (learning by books; $M \approx 66,8\%$). The 95% confidence intervals indicate minimum overlap, that suggests a substantial difference between Groups A and B. The independent samples t-test also proved that the difference in test scores was statistically significant ($p < .05$). Furthermore, this indicates that the use of TurboLearn online platform as a study tool leads to significantly higher test performance compared to the study with books.

Conclusion

AI-driven tools and platforms enhance language teaching and testing, providing immediate feedback and tailored learning paths. While traditional textbook-based learning remains valuable for structured knowledge acquisition, the process of combining it with AI-supported online platforms can accelerate language proficiency and improve testing processes. The online platform TurboLearn is highly recommended for the revision and learning of Business English as well as the online testing platform examica offers wide opportunities for online scoring and grading.

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